

Circularly Polarized Beams Phase Transformation via Tunable Liquid Crystal Periodic Structure

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Nematic liquid crystal elements spatially structured in the azimuthal direction represent a special type diffraction grating capable of achieving a diffraction efficiency of up to 100%. This paper is devoted to the development and study of the spatial polarization properties of a liquid crystal diffraction polarizing twist element, in which a phase profile equivalent to a diffraction polarizing grating is realized by spatially modulating the topology of the director orientation using the method of polarization holographic recording of surface anisotropy in the azo dye AtA-2 layer. The efficient electrical control possibility of the diffraction and the structured element polarization properties, their ambivalence when changing the side of light input into the liquid crystal element are experimentally demonstrated. The optimal value of the external control voltage corresponding to the maximum diffraction efficiency above 90% for circularly polarized radiation is determined.

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1. Introduction

Diffraction gratings are one of the key optical components and are widely used in many fields of science and technology [1–5]. Much attention is paid to the development of electrically tunable diffraction elements to control the spatial, phase, and polarization light characteristics.

Nematic liquid crystals (NLCs) are the most suitable functional materials to create electrically controlled diffraction gratings [6–12]. Their main feature is a combination of properties such as high optical anisotropy ($\Delta n \sim 0.1 - 0.4$), molecular mobility and sensitivity to an external electric field [13–15]. Spatially structured elements based on liquid crystals demonstrate impressive results due to their excellent optical and polarization-selective properties [16–20].

The formation of a spatially modulated NLC director distribution can be obtained using

contactless photoorientation technology [21–23] using holographic recording, which allows precise control of the NLC director distribution on the substrate and makes it possible to form locally inhomogeneous diffraction structures.

A trend of modern optical technologies is the use of the polarization holographic photoorientation method for the construction of electrically switchable diffraction elements based on the use of orthogonally polarized light beams. Phase gratings based on the recording of surface anisotropy by parallel polarized beams are limited by the diffraction efficiency (40%). Meanwhile, the diffraction elements, the director orientation of which was set by exposing the interference pattern of orthogonally polarized circular waves, are characterized by an asymmetric diffraction pattern and theoretically can reach a diffraction efficiency of up to 100% [24].

The purpose of this work is development and optimization of the properties of an electrically controlled liquid crystal grating with a spatially modulated NLC director twist orientation to

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implement effective control of the spatial and polarization light beams characteristics.

2. Fabrication technology

The creation of a locally inhomogeneous twist polarizing microstructure was carried out using the technology of nematic liquid crystal textured photoorientation.

The diffraction element is a sandwich-type NLC cell with an air gap thickness of $10 \mu\text{m}$ (see Figure 1). The inner surfaces of the NLC element glass substrates contain a uniform transparent electrode. To set the initial microstructured orientation of the NLC, the conductive surface on one substrate was coated with a thin film (about 30 nm) of the photosensitive azo dye AtA-2 [25] with an absorption band in the range of 450-520 nm and on the other substrate with a thin film of the orienting polymer Nylon-6 subjected to a mechanical rubbing procedure [26] (see Figure 2a).

FIG. 1. (Color online) Structural scheme of the liquid crystal twist element.

The AtA-2 film acquires orienting properties when exposed to linearly polarized light. The direction of induced orientation of the azo dye molecules is perpendicular to the direction of the activating radiation polarization. LC-1289 ($\Delta n = 0.18$ for a wavelength of 632.8 nm, NIOPIC, Russia) was used in the work. The orientation anisotropy of the azo dye AtA-2 was formed according to the Leith-Upatnieks holographic scheme by orthogonally polarized signal and reference beams with circular polarization at a wavelength of 450 nm. In this case, the interference field is a periodically modulated distribution of linearly

polarized light with different inclination angles of the polarization vector. Under interference field influence, the orientation of the photoorientant azo dye molecules occurs, which leads to spatial modulation of the NLC director orientation (see Figure 2b).

FIG. 2. (Color online) Orientation distributions of the NLC director in the border to Nylon-6 (a) and AtA-2 (b) areas. c) The liquid crystal director orientation distribution in the twist polarizing diffraction structure (top view).

The period of the formed polarizing twist structure is $\Lambda = 20 \mu\text{m}$ and is determined by a change in the azimuthal orientation angle of the director in the NLC layer of an amount equal to 2π . The middle of the period corresponds to an area in which there is no change in the azimuthal angle along the thickness of the liquid crystal ($\varphi_{twist} = 0$). At the same time, the domains that border the structure period are characterized by the rotation of the director to $\varphi_{twist} = -\pi$ and $\varphi_{twist} = +\pi$. Figure 2c shows the top view of the cell, demonstrating the orientation topology of the NLC director within a period of the formed polarizing twist structure.

3. Results

To study the diffraction properties of the formed NLC structure and determine

the polarization transformation patterns of transmitted and diffracted radiation when changing the applied electric voltage, circularly polarized radiation at wavelength $\lambda = 632.8$ nm of the He-Ne laser, a CMOS (complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor) camera and a polarimeter were used. Using the Arbitrary Waveform Generator B-332 (LANFOR Company, St. Petersburg, Russia), an external control voltage with a frequency of 1 kHz was applied to the NLC element electrodes.

The diffraction efficiency was calculated using the formula $\eta_m = \frac{I_m}{I_0} \cdot 100\%$, where I_m is the light beam intensity in the m diffraction order, I_0 is the total light intensity at the output of the NLC element.

The electro-optical response of the NLC structure makes it possible to effectively control the diffraction properties of the grating using an external electric field. Figure 3 presents experimental diffraction patterns formed by a polarizing twist NLC grating in the absence of a control voltage and when applying the optimal voltage values corresponding to the maximum diffraction efficiency value in the second diffraction order (91%). The images were obtained at different polarization states of the incident radiation and with the input of radiation from both the photoorientant AtA-2 and the orientant Nylon-6 sides. A feature of the formed diffraction patterns is the asymmetric diffraction, which depends on the polarization state of the laser beam incident on the grating. The intensity distribution in the observed diffraction pattern is also influenced by the side of the entrance to the element radiation.

In the absence of voltage, the NLC cell functions as a polarizing twist structure. When a voltage is applied above a threshold value, liquid crystal molecules tend to reorient along electric field lines (in our case homeotropically, Fredericks transition [13]). When the electric field reaches a voltage value on cell electrodes typically greater than 2.5 V, the NLC director in the central region of the cell is oriented homeotropically and the twist structure disintegrates (disruption of

FIG. 3. (Color online) Diffraction patterns of circular left and right polarized He-Ne laser radiation at the values of the external control voltage on the NLC element $U = 0$ V, $U = 2.57$ V and $U = 2.80$ V for different input layers Nylon-6 (a) or AtA-2 (b).

the Mauguin regime [27]) with the formation of two independent NLC sublayers. The sublayer bordering the orientant Nylon-6 is characterized by an azimuthal angle uniformity, while the second sublayer adjacent to the azo dye AtA-2 is azimuthal microstructured.

Figures 4 and 5 demonstrate the results of an experimental study of the polarization state transformation of transmitted and diffracted radiation with a change in the amplitude of the applied external electric voltage at the input of circularly polarized radiation into the element from both AtA-2 and Nylon-6 sides, respectively. As can be seen from the polarization diagrams, the twist NLC element makes it possible to effectively control the polarization state of transmitted and diffracted beams at low voltage values. A key feature of the element's operation is the simultaneous formation of two beams with orthogonal circular polarizations in ± 2 diffraction orders when circularly polarized radiation passes into the element from the Nylon-6 side and at a control voltage value of $U = 4.50$ V (see Figure 5). We also note the polarization dependence of the radiation diffracted in orders ± 1 and ± 2 on the orienting layers AtA-2 and Nylon-6 passage sequence.

FIG. 4. (Color online) Polarization diagrams of light beams with circular left and right polarization diffracted in 0, ± 1 and ± 2 diffraction orders versus of the control voltage on the NLC cell changes in the case of radiation input into the element from AtA-2 side.

FIG. 5. (Color online) Polarization diagrams of light beams with circular left and right polarization diffracted in 0, ± 1 and ± 2 diffraction orders versus of the control voltage on the NLC cell changes in the case of radiation input into the element from Nylon-6 side.

4. Discussion

Thus, the NLC grating with a twist director orientation was created. The diffraction

of circularly polarized light beams was studied under varying applied voltage. The conditions for controlling the energy, spatial, and polarization characteristics of the light beams were optimized. It is shown that as the voltage increases, the NLC director is reoriented in the cell volume and the Mauguin condition [27] is disrupted. In this case, the NLC structure can be divided into two regions, one of which provides polarization plane rotation, and the second leads to a phase shift. The effective grating period is reduced by half, while the main feature is related to the difference in diffraction of circularly polarized light beams with right and left polarizations and the possibility of achieving a diffraction efficiency by an order of magnitude with a value close to the limit ($\sim 100\%$). The following operating modes have been experimentally implemented: 1) dividing the input signal into several optical channels; 2) transmitting the input signal to a second optical channel (diffraction order) with an efficiency of 91%; 3) controlling the polarization state of the transmitted radiation using an external electric field and changing the side of the input to the incident radiation element; 4) simultaneous formation of two beams with orthogonal circular polarizations when circularly polarized radiation enters the NLC element from the Nylon-6 side at a control voltage value of 4.50 V.

The fabricated polarizing twist NLC element is characterized by high diffraction efficiency and is of interest for the laser radiation control systems development, allowing controlling the intensity and polarization of light beams diffracted in various orders using a low control voltage.

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